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THE USE OF THE ART OF TAZAD IN THE POETRY OF THE POETESS SHAMS

Abstract. Tazad (Arabic: contrast) is a way of using words expressing contradictory concepts in conjunction with each other for a certain aesthetic purpose. Allama and poet Sheikh Ahmad ibn Khudoidad Tarazi called Tazad Almutazad. Atullah Mahmud Husayni said that tazad was also called "mutabaqa", "tibaq", "tatbiq" and "takafu". Shams Qais Razi called "tazad" "mutobiqa".

``Taqobul is a combination of two words that are mutually exclusive (negation of each other) among the meanings of the word. if the contrast between the colors is extreme, like black and white, then it is contrast, if the contrast is not extreme, like between black and red, it is contrast.

Keywords: Sheikh Ahmad ibn Khudoidad Tarazi, Shams Qais Razi, Taqobul.

Alloma said that according to the level of opposition, the conflict is divided into several types. In short, the conflict is the confrontation of contradictory things and concepts, and at the same time, their basis is the unity of the object, which embodies the contradictory concepts, and the effective opening of this object and an active attitude towards it in the heart of the student. consists of awakening.

On the surface, contrast is similar to antithesis - both of them deal with opposite concepts, and at the same time, they have different aspects. In antithesis, conflicting opposites come from two independent sources, while in antithesis, conflicting opposites have a single source: one thing contains the origin of both good and evil:

You expose all your good and bad,
You are my familiar-stranger heart [Devon page 79]

In this case, evil and good are contradictory concepts and they collide, but at the same time, the source of both feelings is the same lover. In this way, the art of tazad was created.

it should be noted that contrast has common aspects with parallelism and oxymoron..that is, parallelism compares equal and compatible things, oxymoron creates an image by juxtaposing two mutually exclusive things, and contrast compares concepts originating from the same source (opposite things). from this it can be seen that parallelism, oxymoron, antithesis, contrast are separate arts that differ from each other.

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

Tazad is used in poetry, prose, and drama. this art is widely used not only in the literature of the past, but also in our current literature. We pay attention to the extent to which the poetess Shams used the art of tazad:

You are day, I am night. Our paths diverge.

Two eyes full of zer-u-zabar. [devon p. 99]

In this verse, the art of contrast is created by means of the words you and me, night and day. It means that you and I are far from each other and our paths diverge. We are so different from each other that you are night and I am day. That is, they contradict each other, and there is no possibility to see one. Probably for this reason, both eyes are in a bad condition.

I wanted to enjoy Dahr's garden for a moment,

There is joy in grief, and mourning in joy. [Devon p. 56]

In this verse, the art of tazad is revealed through the words of grief and joy, joy and mourning. Here, it is mentioned that the lover wants pleasure even for a moment from the garden of dahr, that is, the garden of the world. but he insists that he was faced with grief and mourning even at this moment.

If I swallow a drop from your lips,

My lips are exposed, one by one, [Devon p. 81]

In this verse, the words "exposed" and "hidden" have opposite meanings. used in the form of the meanings of nihon-hidden, fosh- to be revealed. A lover falls in love with his lips and eyes to such an extent that he dreams of swallowing a drop of it. The poetess describes the beautiful land with such qualities.

The pain of smoking - I'm thankful that I saw peace,

The poet is very satisfied, from the blood of the gift [Devon p. 93]

In this verse, the art of tazad is revealed through the words of pain and pleasure. In this, it is said that the lover is grateful for all the pains and sufferings he has endured. It is said that the poetess is satisfied with her fate.

Doomsday is more than love,

You are prosperous, you are my broken heart [devon p. 79]

In this verse, the art of contrast is revealed through the words prosperity and destruction. It is said that the lover even reaches the end of his life in the agony of love. As a result, he is disappointed.

In your eyes, every king-u gadoga, Rabbano,

If it falls on your horse with zikr, Rabbano. [devon page 7]

In this verse, the art of tazad is revealed through the words shah and gado. In this regard, both kings and kings are addressed as Rabbano, that is, my god. If you want to praise the name of God, look to God.

There is nothing in the human world as abstract as the human heart,

Then you planted a flower and a thorn together. [devon page 33]

In this verse, the art of tazad is revealed through the words flower and thorn. In the verse, it is said that there is nothing in this world as abstract as the human heart, and the flower and the thorn were created together.

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

In conclusion, we can see that Poet Shams skillfully used the art of tazad in her ghazals. With the help of these words, we learned the meaning of opposite words.

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KNOWLEDGE